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Original Article

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Global Research Trends and Collaboration Networks in Paraphimosis: A Bibliometric Analysis of Web of Science Publications (2000–2024)

ABSTRACT

Background: Paraphimosis is a rare but clinically significant urological emergency that can lead to ischemic necrosis or penile loss if not promptly managed. Despite its clinical importance, the global research landscape on paraphimosis has not been systematically evaluated.

Methods: A bibliometric analysis was conducted using the Web of Science Core Collection database. Original research articles published in English between 2000 and 2024 in journals indexed within the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE) were included. Case reports, reviews, and non-original studies were excluded. Data were processed with Microsoft Excel (2016) and BibExcel, while VOSviewer (version 1.6.20) was used to generate visual maps. Analyses included co-authorship, co-occurrence, and bibliographic coupling, with productivity and impact assessed by

citation counts, h-index, and citation sum within the h-core.

Results: A total of 421 publications were retrieved, of which 130 original articles met the inclusion criteria. These involved 564 authors from 30 countries and were published in 76 journals. The United States was the most productive country, followed by Turkey, Germany, and the United Kingdom. *Urology* and the *Journal of Sexual Medicine* had the highest h-indices among journals. Keyword analysis showed that “paraphimosis,” “penile strangulation,” and “penile incarceration” were predominant, whereas diagnostic methods, treatment strategies, and long-term outcomes were underrepresented. Bibliographic coupling revealed fragmented clusters with limited international collaboration.

Conclusions: This study provides the first comprehensive bibliometric mapping of paraphimosis research. Findings underscore the need for larger-scale, multicenter, and prospective studies, particularly involving low- and middle-income countries.

Keywords: Paraphimosis; Penis; Urologic Emergencies; Bibliometrics; interinstitutional Relations

Introduction

Paraphimosis is an acute urological condition characterized by rapidly progressive edema and circulatory impairment resulting from the retracted prepuce becoming trapped behind the glans penis. If prompt diagnosis and treatment are not established, serious complications such as ischemic necrosis and even partial penile loss may occur (1, 2). Although it is a rare presentation in emergency departments, delayed diagnosis can lead to permanent sequelae with significant functional and cosmetic consequences (3).

Paraphimosis cases most commonly occur iatrogenically following catheterization, but may also arise due to traumatic factors such as penile strangulation by foreign bodies or, less frequently, spontaneously (4). This condition tends to follow a more severe course in low-resource healthcare systems, where limited urological expertise and delayed presentation are common (5). However, the majority of publications in the literature consist of case reports and small case series, while studies providing systematic data remain considerably scarce (6).

Bibliometric analysis is a powerful method used to examine scientific productivity, citation impact, collaboration networks, and thematic trends within a given field (7)

It is particularly valuable for rare and underexplored clinical conditions, as it contributes to the assessment of research trends in areas where clinical studies are limited (8). This approach can identify leading countries and institutions, highlight journals that play a central role in the publication process, and reveal predominant research topics, thereby guiding future investigations (9).

In the current literature, no comprehensive bibliometric mapping study focusing on paraphimosis has been identified. To address this gap, the present study employed the Web of Science Core Collection database to analyze publication trends, citation impact, leading authors, institutions, journals, and research collaborations in the field of paraphimosis using bibliometric methods. The aim of this study is to elucidate the structure of existing scientific output on a global scale and to provide a foundation that may guide future research.

Materials And Methods

The Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection database was used for the bibliometric analysis. To retrieve the data, the “topic” (TS) search field available in the WoS system was employed. The search strategy included the following keywords: TS=("paraphimosis" OR "penile strangulation" OR "foreskin entrapment"

OR "penile incarceration" OR "penile constriction" OR "penile entrapment" OR "penile tourniquet syndrome" OR "balanopreputial strangulation" OR "acute phimosis"). Data extraction for this study was conducted on September 1, 2025.

Original research articles published in English between 2000 and 2024 in journals indexed within the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE) of the WoS database were included in this study. Articles were selected based on searches performed with the predetermined keywords. Publications other than original research articles (e.g., case reports, case series, narrative reviews, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses) were excluded.

Microsoft Excel (version 2016) was used for data organization, analysis, and visualization.¹⁰ For the processing of bibliometric data, BibExcel (version 2016-02-20) was employed.¹¹ The analysis identified the most productive authors, countries, and journals. For each category, the number of articles, total citations (cit), h-index (h-i), and citation sum within the h-core (CSh) were calculated. The top five most productive and influential authors were reported for each category.

Visual maps were generated using the VOSviewer software (version 1.6.20).⁷

Co-authorship analysis, co-occurrence analysis, and bibliographic coupling methods were employed in the study. Full counting was chosen as the counting method for all analyses. To normalize the strength of the links between items, the association strength method was applied. In order to achieve a more reliable layout, the starting point was set at 1000 random starts (random start=1000), allowing the algorithm to identify the most suitable distribution from different initial positions. The maximum number of iterations was also set at 1000 (max iterations=1000). These parameters were applied to enhance the consistency of the results and to ensure convergence toward a more general optimum rather than a local minimum. In the network maps, each item was represented as a node, while the relationships between nodes were illustrated as links.

In the co-authorship analysis, collaboration among institutions was examined, and the overlay visualization method was applied for this purpose. In this visualization, colors indicate the temporal distribution of institutional publications: institutions with more recent publications are represented in yellow, while those with older publications are shown in purple. Each node in the map represents an institution, with its size and label reflecting the institution's

significance. Only the most prominent institutions are labeled in the visualization. The lines between nodes indicate inter-institutional collaboration; short lines represent stronger relationships, while longer lines indicate weaker connections. Thicker lines signify stronger collaboration. For filtering in the network map, the minimum number of documents per institution was set at 1 and the minimum number of citations at 10. The number of documents was used as the weighting measure, with larger nodes representing institutions with more publications. In the overlay visualization analysis, the average publication year (APY) values were used as the criterion.

Relationships among keywords were identified using co-occurrence analysis. This method was employed to determine the conceptual structure of the research field. The analysis was performed based on the keywords specified by the authors in the included articles. In the visualization generated through the network visualization method, the associations between the most frequently used terms and other related terms were demonstrated. In the map, each keyword was represented by a node, while the lines between nodes reflected the frequency with which these terms co-occurred within the same publication. The size of each node

indicated the total frequency of the corresponding keyword. A minimum threshold of 2 was applied for keyword inclusion, thereby highlighting the most frequently used and field-specific concepts in the literature.

Bibliographic coupling analysis was conducted to demonstrate studies with similar citation histories and to identify research clusters within the literature. A minimum citation threshold of 10 was applied in the analysis. Citation counts were used to determine the strength of the links, with each node in the map representing an article and node size reflecting the number of citations. Colors were used to distinguish groups of publications with similar citation patterns.

Results

The predefined search strategy on the Web of Science database retrieved a total of 421 publications related to paraphimosis. After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 130 original research articles were identified. These articles were authored by 564 contributors from 30 countries and were published across 76 journals. The flow diagram is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flow diagram of the study selection process

The authors with the highest h-index were Detweiler MB (h-i: 2, CSh: 34) and Nyirady Peter (h-i: 2, CSh: 7), while those with the highest citation sum within the h-core (CSh) were Patorno Elisabetta (1 article, 116 citations), Schneeweiss Sebastian (1 article, 116 citations), and Dave Chintan V (1 article, 116 citations) (Table 1).

The United States (USA) ranked first in terms of the highest number of articles, CSh, and h-index (h-i: 12, 47 articles, 391 CSh). Following the USA in terms of h-index were Turkey (h-i: 5, 6 articles), Germany (h-i: 4, 4 articles), and the United Kingdom (UK) (h-i: 4, 8 articles) (Table 1).

The two journals with the highest h-index were Urology (7 articles, 109 CSh, h-i: 5) and the Journal of Sexual Medicine (7 articles, 83 CSh, h-i: 5). The journals with the highest CSh scores were JCPSP – Journal of the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (2 articles, 116 CSh, h-i: 1), Urology (7 articles, 109 CSh, h-i: 5), and Veterinary Clinics of North America – Equine Practice (1 article, 91 CSh, h-i: 1) (Table 1).

The countries with the highest number of publications are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 3 illustrates temporal collaboration among institutions. Out of a total of 212 institutions, 62 that had at least one publication and a minimum of 10 citations were included in the co-authorship analysis. The number of documents was used as the weighting measure. Some institutions were not connected to others; the largest connected cluster consisted of 15 institutions. In total, two clusters and 70 links were identified. Strong collaborations among institutions were particularly evident between 2010 and 2014. The institution with the highest number of articles, the highest citation count (cit), and the greatest total link strength (TLS) was the University of California, San Francisco (3 articles, 129 citations, 14 TLS). The institution with the second-highest number of publications was Texas A&M University (3 articles, 22 citations, 0 TLS). The institution with the second-highest citation count was Harvard Medical School (1 article, 116 citations, 0 TLS). The average publication year (APY) of the University of California, San Francisco was 2010.33.

Figure 4 presents the frequency and interrelationships of keywords appearing together in the same publications, as identified through co-occurrence analysis. A minimum threshold of at least two publications per keyword was applied. Out of a total of 281 keywords, 39 met this criterion, all of which were found to be interconnected. The analysis was conducted on these 38 keywords. As a

result, six clusters, 97 links, and a total link strength (TLS) of 151 were obtained. Occurrence frequency was used as the weighting measure. The most frequently co-occurring keywords were paraphimosis (23 occurrences, 37 TLS), penis (16 occurrences, 27 TLS), penile strangulation (15 occurrences, 21 TLS), and circumcision (9 occurrences, 9 TLS).

Figure 5 displays the network map illustrating the associations of the most frequently used keyword, paraphimosis, with other terms. The keyword paraphimosis was located within Cluster 1 and was observed to be connected with all clusters. It had 23 occurrences, 16 links, and a total link strength (TLS) of 37.

In Figure 6, a network visualization was generated using bibliographic coupling analysis to identify relationships among documents with similar citation histories. Only documents that had received at least 10 citations were included in the analysis. Of the 130 documents, 34 met this criterion, and 16 of these were found to be interconnected. Citation count was used as the weighting measure. As a result, four clusters, 43 links, and a total link strength (TLS) of 126 were obtained. The documents with the highest citation counts were Dave (2019) (116 citations, 0 TLS), Morris (91 citations, 14 TLS), Hellwig (2000) (61 citations, 0 TLS), Lerman (2001) (61 citations, 16 TLS), and Ivanovski (2007) (47 citations, 39 TLS). The documents with the highest total link strength were Ivanovski (2007) (47 citations, 39 TLS), Noh (2004) (35 citations, 26 TLS), Detweiler

(2001) (30 citations, 23 TLS), Santucci (2004) citations, 21 TLS).
(25 citations, 23 TLS), and Singh (2010) (15

Figure 2. Treemap visualization of the countries with the highest number of publications on paraphimosis (The numbers next to the countries represent the total number of articles)

Figure 3. Overlay visualization map of organizations co-authorships

Figure 4. Author keywords appearing at least twice were subjected to co-occurrence analysis and visualized through network visualization

Figure 5. Network map illustrating the co-occurrence relationships between the most frequently used keyword ‘paraphimosis’ and other associated terms

Figure 6. Bibliographic coupling analysis illustrating the connections among documents

Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of scientific publications on paraphimosis, thereby addressing a significant gap in the literature. The findings revealed that, despite being a rare but clinically critical emergency condition, the body of scientific output on paraphimosis remains relatively limited. An evaluation of 130 original research articles retrieved from the Web of Science database demonstrated that publications were largely concentrated around a small number of authors, a limited range of countries, and specific journals. Consistent with prior reports, these results confirm that most of the existing literature on paraphimosis is restricted to case reports and small case series.^{12,13}

The United States was identified as the country with the highest number of publications and citations, while Turkey, Germany, and the United Kingdom provided lower but noteworthy contributions. This finding indicates that countries with high scientific capacity in the field of urological emergencies are at the forefront of research production.¹⁴ Conversely, the limited contributions from low- and middle-income countries may be attributed to restricted academic infrastructure, insufficient research funding, and a shortage of urological expertise in these regions.⁵ This observation supports clinical findings that emergency conditions such as paraphimosis tend to follow a more severe course in resource-limited healthcare systems.¹⁵

At the journal level, *Urology* and the *Journal of Sexual Medicine* emerged as the journals with the highest h-index and citation impact. This suggests that the most influential publications in the field are generally disseminated through urology and sexual health journals. However, the dispersion of articles across different specialty journals indicates that research output in this area possesses an interdisciplinary character.¹⁶

Keyword analysis revealed that the most frequently used terms were “paraphimosis,” “penile strangulation,” and “penile incarceration.” This finding indicates that clinical research has primarily focused on complications and etiological factors. In contrast, themes such as diagnostic methods, treatment algorithms, and long-term outcomes appear to be underrepresented in the literature. This gap highlights an important opportunity for future research.¹⁷

The bibliographic coupling analysis demonstrated that most of the studies in the literature have progressed in small, disconnected clusters. This finding suggests that strong and sustainable scientific collaborations among researchers have not yet been fully established. However, the literature emphasizes that international collaborations play a critical role in

improving research quality, particularly for rare and underexplored clinical conditions.¹⁸ Similarly, in the field of paraphimosis, it is evident that broader, multicenter, prospective studies based on standardized methodologies are needed.

The findings of this study further highlight the value of bibliometric analysis as a useful approach for rare clinical conditions. Indeed, bibliometrics not only evaluates the quantity of research output but also provides insight into thematic trends, research collaborations, and the scientific impact of publications.¹⁹ In this way, knowledge gaps can be clearly identified even in areas where clinical studies are limited, thereby offering a roadmap for future research.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the bibliometric analysis was conducted exclusively using the Web of Science Core Collection database. Therefore, publications indexed in other databases such as Scopus, PubMed, or Google Scholar were not included. This may have resulted in the exclusion of certain studies published in regional or local journals. Second, only original research articles published in English in journals indexed within the SCIE were included. Consequently, case reports, reviews, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses were excluded, and publications in other languages were not represented in the

analysis. This may have led to the omission of some important clinical contributions in the literature. Third, the bibliometric indicators used in this study (e.g., h-index, total citation count, citation sum within the h-core) provide only indirect information regarding the quality of publications. These metrics may not fully reflect the true clinical impact of the studies or their contribution to patient care. Fourth, the network maps generated through the software used (BibExcel, VOSviewer) are dependent on the selected algorithmic parameters. Different parameters or alternative software might yield different visualizations and clustering outcomes. Therefore, methodological limitations should be considered when interpreting the results. Finally, due to the retrospective design of the study, a detailed evaluation of the clinical content of the publications was not feasible; instead, the analysis was restricted to bibliometric measures. Thus, the findings provide a general overview of scientific productivity and research trends in paraphimosis, rather than directly reflecting clinical outcomes in its management.

Conclusion

This study presents the first comprehensive bibliometric mapping analysis of the literature on paraphimosis. The findings demonstrate that the number of studies published on this rare

urological emergency remains limited, with the majority of existing publications consisting of case reports and small case series, and international collaborations being insufficient. The most productive countries were identified as the United States and European nations, while Turkey stood out with a relatively high citation impact. Furthermore, the research output was found to be concentrated in a limited number of journals, with restricted thematic diversity.

These findings clearly underscore the need for larger-scale, prospective, and multicenter clinical studies in the field of paraphimosis. Moreover, the limited contributions from low- and middle-income countries highlight the necessity of strengthening healthcare infrastructure and academic capacity in these regions. Bibliometric analysis serves as a valuable tool for identifying knowledge gaps in the existing literature on such rare and underexplored clinical conditions, thereby guiding future research directions.

In conclusion, this study systematically delineated the current state of research on paraphimosis and provided a comprehensive framework regarding scientific productivity, collaborations, and thematic trends. The findings are expected to guide future studies and contribute indirectly to clinical decision-making processes.

No	Authors	All articles	Citation sum within h-core	All citations	h-index
1	Detweiler MB	2	34	34	2
2	Nyirady, Peter	2	7	7	2
3	Patorno, Elisabetta	1	116	116	1
4	Schneeweiss, Sebastian	1	116	116	1
5	Dave Chintan V	1	116	116	1
No	Countries	All articles	Citation sum within h-core	All citations	h-index
1	USA	47	391	548	12
2	Türkiye	6	27	29	5
3	Germany	4	86	86	4
4	UK	8	28	30	4
5	Australia	5	105	108	3
No	Journal Names	All articles	Citation sum within h-core	All citations	h-index
1	Urology	7	109	86	5
2	Journal of Sexual Medicine	7	83	113	5
3	Journal of Emergency Medicine	6	27	32	4
4	Urologia Internationalis	4	23	23	4
5	Javma-Journal of The American Veterinary Medical Association	3	39	41	3

Table 1. The top 5 most productive and influential authors, countries and journals in the field of paraphimosis

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